

Glossary of terms: research, science and technology meets complex systems

This glossary contains a list of terms used throughout various submissions to the Te Ara Paerangi Future Pathways Green Paper, and other reports and working papers generated in support of the submissions. The definitions in this document describe the specific meanings that have been attached to the term.

Term	Definition
Chatham House Rule	“When a meeting, or part thereof, is held under the Chatham House Rule, participants are free to use the information received, but neither the identity nor the affiliation of the speaker(s), nor that of any other participant, may be revealed.” ¹
Compact between science and society	Science has been expected to produce ‘reliable’ knowledge, provided merely that it communicates its discoveries to society. ² A system of trust is generated through this, with protection provided to the fundamentals through Government policy.
Crises	Problems that are urgent and require immediate attention.
Early career researcher (ECR)	Masters' and PhD student researchers, and postgraduate researchers up to 10 years post terminal degree (not counting extended leave). Often but not necessarily precariously employed.
Exploitation	Conditions leading to unsustainable growth (see Gunderson & Holling 2002 ³)
Hypercompetitive	A situation of extreme competition. For research funding, this can be a situation where success rates remain low amongst a high number of applications.
Intersectional Diversity	Intersectionality is the overlapping or intersecting of identities and their experiences of oppression and discrimination. Intersectionality recognises not only differences between identities (such as racial, gender, and LGBT+ identities) but within these. Addressing diversity issues through an intersectional lens

	accounts for the different issues individuals may face and acknowledges that not all diversity problems can be solved with a single solution.
Leverage Points	These are places within a complex system (a corporation, an economy, a living body, a city, an ecosystem) where a small shift in one thing can produce big changes in everything. ⁴
Ostrom's Principles	Identifying core underlying "best practices" or factors (i.e., rules and structures) that characterise robust institutions for the governance of common-pool resources ⁵ .
Overhead	The extra cost institutions apply to grants and contracts over salaries and direct expenses. This can be compared to indirect costs in other systems, or some time referred to as Facilities and Administrative costs (example, and has been compared historically in the US).
Panacea	A single solution that will solve all problems.
Ponzi Scheme	A Ponzi scheme is a form of fraud that lures investors and pays profits to earlier investors with funds from more recent investors. Not to be mistaken with a pyramid scheme, a ponzi scheme is an investor trap that continually generates victims within the system, similar to the increasing number of PhD students entering the workforce with very few jobs available to them.
Poverty Traps	A poverty trap and a rigidity trap are typical maladaptive departures from an adaptive cycle in a system. "If an adaptive cycle collapses because the potential and diversity have been eradicated due to misuse or an external force, an impoverished state can result, with low connectedness, low potential, and low resilience, thus creating a poverty trap." ⁶
Precarious employment	Precarious employment describes continuous short term contracts that may or may not lead to permanent employment. Precarious employment is rife within academia in New Zealand ⁷ , and the research community ⁸ in general. Those most affected by this are often Early Career Researchers (ECRs).

Principle Investigator (PI)	Term used to describe a “research group leader”. A PI will refer to an active researcher with potential funding available for doctoral and postdoctoral researchers.
Rich get richer	Shorthand for a system where those with resources accumulate success because they were well resourced, and not due to the merit of their proposals. Also known as the ‘Matthew Effect’. Work to date suggests this applies to the NZ research system.
Rigidity Traps	A poverty trap and a rigidity trap are typical maladaptive departures from an adaptive cycle in a system. “A system with high potential, connectedness, and resilience is represented by the rigidity trap. It is suggestive of the maladaptive conditions present in hierocracies, such as large bureaucracies.” ⁶
Silo	In the context of a research environment, a silo generates an area where certain researchers are isolated and disconnected from others.
Urgent	The use of urgency in submissions describes many crises that ought to be fixed sooner rather than later. The Te Ara Paerangi Future Pathways process aims to take place over multiple years although the problems it aims to address are a reality for many now.

References

- (1) Chatham House Rule <https://www.chathamhouse.org/about-us/chatham-house-rule> (accessed 2022 -03 -15).
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- (3) Holling, C. S.; Gunderson, L. H. *Resilience and Adaptive Cycles*; Washington, D.C.: Island Press, 2002.
- (4) Meadows, D. H.; Wright, D. *Thinking in Systems : A Primer*, 2008.
- (5) Ostrom, E. *Governing the Commons : The Evolution of Institutions for Collective Action*, 1990.
- (6) Holling, C. S. Understanding the Complexity of Economic, Ecological, and Social Systems. *Ecosystems*, 2001, 4, 390–405. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10021-001-0101-5>.
- (7) Simpson, A.; Jolliffe Simpson, A. D.; Soar, M.; Oldfield, L.; Roy, R. P.; Salter, L. A. *Elephant In The Room: Precarious Work In New Zealand Universities*; report; The University of Auckland, 2022. <https://doi.org/10.17608/k6.auckland.19243626.v2>.
- (8) Research precariat - OECD <https://www.oecd.org/sti/science-technology-innovation-outlook/research-precariat/> (accessed 2022 -03 -17).